

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B135
Date: 27 Sep 2005
Take Off 12:08:31
Landing: 16:34:30
Flight Time 4h25m59

Campaign: ICEPIC
Operating Area: West Scotland

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Graham Morgan	BAE Systems
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Phil Brown	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
6	Flight Manager training / CCM2	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
8	CVI	Stuart Heath	FAAM
9	CCN	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
10	AMS	James Allan	University of Manchester
11	SID	Edwin Hurst	University of Herfordshire
16	SID	Richard Greenaway	University of Herfordshire
17	Mission Scientist 2	Richard Cotton	Met Office
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B135 Track 27-SEP-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b135
 Date: 27 Sep 2005
 Project: ICEPIC
 Location: West Scotland

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
113030		INU	0.35 kft	125	set to navigate
113305		Start pos	0.35 kft	125	52'04.36N 0'37.50W
120831		Take off		328	Cranfield
121500		ASP opened	12.1 kft	322	
122621		Lower clear	18.1 kft	294	removed
122644		lower clear	18.0 kft	294	replaced
122659		lower red	18.0 kft	293	removed
122716		lower red	18.0 kft	294	replaced
122739		lower sil	18.0 kft	295	removed
122754		lower sil	18.0 kft	295	replaced
122815		lower j	18.0 kft	294	removed
122832		lower j	18.0 kft	294	replaced
123131		BBRs retract	18.1 kft	293	retract cover
123256		BBRs extend	18.0 kft	289	extend cover
122020		Reached FL180	18.0 kft	297	
130400		Tapes started			recording
130552	132257	profile 1	18.0 - 5.5 kft	299	From FL180
131313		interrupt profile 1	11.1 kft	302	FL40
131343		recomm profile 1	11.1 kft	279	
131443		qnh 995	10.1 kft	275	
131834		interrupt profile 1	6.2 kft	287	5500 ft
132123		recomm Profile 1	4.0 kft	100	turn reciprocal 4kft
134346	134510	Run 1	5.5 kft	353	
134804	134931	Run 2	7.5 kft	188	
135237	135434	Run 3	10.0 kft	028	
135727	140140	Run 4	5.5 kft	359	
140437	140942	Run 5	5.5 kft	198	
141052		tapes changed	8.3 kft	191	
141241	141839	Run 6	8.0 kft	001	
142156	142443	Run 7	7.0 kft	234	
142740	143024	Run 8	8.5 kft	077	
143257	144139	Profile 2	9.0 - 0.5 kft	237	
144146	145044	Run 9	0.5 kft	244	
145210	150207	Run 10	2.0 kft	172	
145431		qnh	2.0 kft	173	1004
150247	153038	Profile 3	2.0 - 27.0 kft	195	
150436		interrupt Profile 3	4.0 kft	071	4000 ft
150550		recomm Profile 3	16.0 - 27.0 kft	167	
151727		interrupt Profile 3			
151840		recomm Profile 3			
153112	161146	Run 11	27.0 kft	209	BBRs test
153146		BBR cover	27.0 kft	206	Retracted
161329		ASP	25.0 kft	126	ASP closed
163022		BBR cover			BBR extend
163430		Land Cranfield	0.32 kft	246	
163927		final position	0.32 kft	307	52'04.36N 0'37.50W

B135 Track 27-SEP-05

PROJECT BRIEF: ICEPIC – development of ice and precipitation in cumulus clouds.

Scientific Aims: The goal of ICEPIC is to understand and quantify the formation and growth of ice particles in cumulus clouds. We wish to examine:

- ❖ the formation of the first ice due to primary nucleation on ice nuclei (IN)
- ❖ the development of ice via secondary processes such as the Hallett-Mossop process, in which new ice particles are generated during the riming growth of ice particles
- ❖ other secondary ice production processes, such as evaporative break-up;
- ❖ the production of supercooled raindrops and their role in the glaciation process
- ❖ the dependence of these processes on the dynamics of the cloud
- ❖ the production of precipitation

As a first priority, in-situ aerosol and microphysical measurements from the aircraft will be gathered. Measurements will be made in cumulus clouds when their tops are about 0°C through to when the tops have grown to about -20°C.

Weather conditions: Developing showers that are forecast to have tops up to about -15°C. A section of air free of ice crystals from higher or older clouds.

Safety: Regions that paint RED on the aircraft weather radar should be avoided. No flight into clouds known to be producing lightning. Information on current location of lightning (sferics) can be provided by FAAM using the NAMIS system.

Key instruments and their operation

Basic meteorology

- Rosemount temperatures, GE hygrometer
- GPS (including GPS Cruciform at 20 Hz), INU, turbulence probe
When in supercooled liquid water, Flight Manager & PIs to monitor turbulence probe signals (TBPC & TBPD) for signs of icing (loss of variability, drop in signal). ICEX to be used on radome, water traps empty.
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC.
When straight & level in clear air, zero / calibrate and note in the Flight Managers log.
- TWC profile ascents or descents should avoid cloud if possible

Cloud Microphysics & Aerosol

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP (or CIP-100), PCASP & SID-2.
Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations, pristine ice crystal habits, large drops ($d > 100 \mu\text{m}$) in 2D imagery above freezing level.
- CPI as above
- CCN measurements should be made by filling the alleviator (2min reqd.) whilst in clear air either below, between or upwind of the cloud layer(s) of interest. Requires altitude to be held for the 10 min of sample & process.
- AMS minimum 2 min (~12km) reqd for size-resolved composition distribution (out of cloud or Option **B** runs) inlet change & on/off messages copied to Flight Managers log
- CVI below cloud base, normal operation is in aerosol mode
above cloud base, normal operation is in CVI mode to sample cloud particle residues into the AMS

Key instruments currently unavailable

- Ice Nucleus counter
(INC) will normally be operated in clear air and under fixed conditions of temperature and supersaturation so as to maintain it in a stable condition. Allow additional time between runs for the operator to adjust it to different conditions.
- FWVS {to preserve lamp life, switch off when dew point above -15°C}
- ADA & SID as for 2D probes

Quicklook to include: TATD & N, DP, LAT, LON, LWC, NEVLW & TW, U, V, W, PHGT, HDG, TAS, TBPC & PD

SORTIE BRIEF: ICEPIC ICE and Precipitation Initiation in Cumulus clouds

Flight Number: B135

Date: 27 September 2005

Mission Scientist: Phil Brown

Sortie Aims: To measure development of microphysics and dynamics in cumulus cloud systems.

Location: Amongst developing cumulus clouds within 1-5 hours transit of Cranfield. Showers expected off and along west coast of Scotland and off north coast of Ireland, Area Charlie, and possibly into Area Bravo. (*Both away from Chilbolton.*)

Sortie Summary:

1.Characterise inflow atmosphere around and below developing cumulus

2.Penetrates cumulus clouds, preferably near the top of growing turrets, through the updraught. All cloud penetrations should be *with wings level*. Three principal options are for:

A well-defined isolated clouds

B many clouds (RICO scenario)

C organised convection on a convergence line or a gust front.

Sortie Detail

1. Out-of-Cloud: only where not done by CSIP

1.1.Take off and climb for transit to the operating area. Locate suitable growing cumulus. 40+ min

1.2.Profile descent in clear air, 1000 ft/min, FL200 to 500 ft agl. If necessary step profile to stay in area. Set altitudes and directions for later[†]. 25 min

1.3.Run at 500 ft agl, minimum time 10 min along suitable azimuth (across line or front for Option C) to sample inflow aerosols & IN. May require initial delay to settle instruments. 10 min

1.4.Ascend to 500 ft below cloud base and carry out 10 min run on suitable azimuth to sample inflow aerosols & IN. May require delay after ascent to settle instruments. 15 min

2. Cloud Work Options

Option A: Isolated developing clouds – ascend with clouds, near their top

A.1.Proceed to about 0° C altitude[†], or below max cloud top if lower 5 min

A.2.Adjust altitude to 500 ft below cloud top and penetrate cloud. The penetration should be made at a constant azimuth and altitude. It is important to penetrate the growing turret, updraught, region. Once clear of cloud, continue run for 10 s then procedure turn to come back to same region of cloud as quickly as possible. 5 min

A.3.Repeat A.2 while appropriate, ascending with the top until growth stops or T = -20°C[†]
{ *Vertical separation of repeats set to match growth of cloud*} 45 min

A.4.Repeat runs at -3 to -8°C T levels where practical, otherwise colder, to measure changes. 15 min

Option B: Many developing cumulus clouds – sample many clouds

B.1.Proceed to 0° C altitude[†], or max cloud top if lower 5 min

B.2.Commence 10 min run in along shear direction[†]. Adjust track to randomly sample growing turret / updraught regions of cloud but without passing through RED radar echoes (reflectivities of 37 dBZ or greater). End run clear of cloud. 10 min

B.3.As time permits, repeat an ascent by -3° C[†] (*approximately* 1500 ft) followed by a run as in B.2 until the lowest of -15° C[†] or max cloud top is reached. (-3, -6, -9, -12, -15° C[†]) 75 min

Option C: Clouds with linear organization (eg. along a convergence line or gust front).

C.1.Proceed to 0° C[†], or max cloud top if lower 5 min

C.2.Fly leg perpendicular to line, length as required. Adjust track to penetrate cloud tops or cell centres. End run clear of cloud. 2 min

C.3. As time permits, repeat a 180° turn and ascent followed by C.2. Ascent either; as **A** to 500 ft below cloud tops until $-20^{\circ}\text{C}^{\dagger}$ reached, or as **B** at fixed temperature levels.

30+ min

3. Repeat If time permits, for new developing cumulus carry out Option **A**, **B** or **C**.

Transit return at any suitable altitude. 40+ min

① MET. SUMMARY. Unstable w/SW flow over Western Isles, behind cold front that passed earlier. 0900 vic image showed classic open cell convection throughout area. Found, as expected, ducts of cells, some deep tops to $\sim -15/-20^{\circ}\text{C}$, with growing cells around the fringes.

② After initial profile F180-4000', some reconnaissance to find ice growing cell.

③ runs had a target cloud at 5500, 7500, 10000 but these were well below cloud top. Precip. obs. Descent into region fringing deeper cells to do random sampling. 2 legs at 5500 & 1 at 8000. Last of these ended up within the mass of deeper convec. 2 more runs at 7500, 8500 ft. Sampled a few cells.

Descent to 500 ft for low level aerosol sampling. Run was initially more or less into wind but turned left to avoid getting too far from home. Further 10 min leg at 2000 ft, changing hdg to avoid precip.

Some pix of radar display on early runs may show orientn of runs w/ precip. Some liquid precip drops seen. Also columns & aggreg. at -8°C . Max updrafts generally small, less than 5ms^{-1} consistent with low CAPE.

WBC peaks $\sim 0.6-0.9\text{ g m}^{-3}$ in cloud penetrations at -5 to -8°C . Cells mostly painted green on w/x radar at time of penetration.

Video should show orientn of cloud runs ok except for legs which were in more continuous cloud masses. eg run 6.

Seems good agreement between JW & NW. NTW picks up regions of ice/precip in later cloud cells.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Phil Brown

Flight No **B**.....135

Date27/9/05.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1208	rah				To Crayfield.
/		6000			2/8 Co 2500ft ish. layers at ~5500 & above.
/		8500			Cloud top - clear above
1234		18000	291		Passing liveopod. Dallas Co over land. No sign of glaciation.
/				Deeper	clouds visible to the N.
1254		"	320	54.2 4.6	Just off 10 Man. 23 mins to 69
/					Patches of deeper Co with glac tops just ahead
1304		"	300		Clouds near start of profile
130552		"	"	55.0N 5.6W	Start P1 avoiding cloud
/		15500			2000 lower layer.
/		14500			-20°C Some tops vis to this level.
131315		10500		55.3 6.3	Hold P1 to reorient
/		9500			-10°C most cells ahead showing green
/					over yellow
/					Sea state 6
/		7000	290		-5°C
131840		5500		-2.5	Hold P1 & turn about.
132123		4000		+1.0	End P1 Looking for cloud.
1h 20 1329					Climbing to FL100 to look
1335					Moving to N of Islay.
/		5500			
/				-1.8	Start 1.1 Cloud top well above
/					Precip already

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.135**
FAAM © 2004

Date **27/9/05**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
		7500			Start 1.2 -5.5
					Yellow on radar
1349					Precip already on the side of cloud.
134931					End.
135237		10000			Start 1.3 -10.5C
135727		5500			Start Run 4 more random sampling
135959		"		-2.2	Good cell ahead. Top ~1500 above.
140140					End R4
		"			Start R5 small cell at start
					Then into fairly solid.
					Several updrafts
140942		"			End 5 Pass good cell just at end.
		8000			-6.9C
141241		"			Start 6. Good cell at start.
					Columns e aggr. W at first
141839		"			Finished in mass of cloud
		7000			Start 7 -5.4
					Precip in 2nd cell.
					3rd cell green, rain.
142463		"		36.9 6.2	End 7 between Figg e Rhom.
		8500			Stable layer near here.
		"			Start 8 -8.4
					1st cell is green.
143024		"			End 8 descend for to level work.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

DEBRIEF ON
REVERSE

Paul Brown

Flight No **B.135**

Date 27/9/05

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
143257		8500			Start P2
					AoA iced up at 143130
144146		500'			Start R9 Fairly into wind.
14448					Turning onto S to continue
145044					End R9
1452'		2000'			Start R10 base ~ 2500
—					Clouds look sim to main
—					operating area.
145636		"			nudging R to avoid precip.
1502		"			End 10
—		2000	195	55.7 6.8	Start P3
—					low level runs were generally upwind of main cloud area
1505-		4000	075		restart P3
		16000			hold P3 & turn about.
—					Some clouds to the N were reaching ~ 14000 with only small signs of glaciation. Tops to 16000 were snow forming
1530		27000			End P3 Start 11
1628		4000			Cloudbase on return.
1635					touchdown Coanfield.
1639					Stationary.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B135

Date: 10/05/05

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	
13:05:52	20	0.08	67								Start Profile 1 from FL180
13:10:25	40	0.09									FL140
13:11:22	100	0.09									FL130
13:12:15	50	0.06									FL120
13:13:12	Noise										FL110
13:14:49	5	0.06									FL100
13:15:45	2	0.06									FL090
13:16:45	5	0.06									FL080
13:17:42	5	0.06									FL070
13:18:38	5	0.06									FL060
13:22:22	10	0.06									FL050
13:22:55	Noise										End of Profile 1 @ 4000'
13:24:00											Logging computer crash
13:57:59	Noise		103								Start Run 4
13:58:00	Noise		104		20	150	1				
14:00:00	Noise		105								
14:01:40											End of Run 4
14:04:40											Start Run 5 @ 5500'
14:05:00	25	0.06	113								
14:07:00	4000	0.3	162		110	800	1	4000			
14:09:00	1200	0.3	226		80	250	1	2000			
14:09:42											End of Run 5
14:12:41											Start Run 6 @ 8000'
14:13:00	Noise		230								
14:15:00	230	0.09	261		55	400	5	40000			
14:17:00	600	0.31	288		200	800	8	10000			
14:18:39											End of Run 6
14:21:57											Start Run 7 @ 7000'
14:22:00	Noise		291								
14:24:00	1000	0.32	346		1600	700	1	35000			
14:24:44											End of Run 7
14:27:40											Start Run 8 @ 8500'
14:28:00	500	0.3	355		40	675	8	10000			
14:30:00	3000	0.3	374		1300	150	1	10000			

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B135

Date: 10/05/05

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
14:30:26											End of Run 8
14:32:57	20	0.06	378								Start Profile 2 from FL090
14:33:50	25	0.06									FL080
14:34:57	15	0.06									FL070
14:35:55	40	0.06									FL060
14:36:54	55	0.06			5	800	8	200			FL050
14:38:00	80	0.06									FL040
14:39:06	90	0.06									FL030
14:40:05	190	0.06									FL020
14:41:56											End of P 2 & Start Run 9 @ 500'
14:42:00	50	0.09									
14:44:00	200	0.06									
14:46:00	150	0.06									
14:48:00	60	0.06	379								
14:50:40											End of Run 9
14:52:11											Start Run 10 @ 2000'
14:53:00	Noise										
14:55:00	Noise										
14:57:00	Noise										
14:59:00	30	0.06									
15:01:00	30	0.06									
15:02:08											End of Run 10
15:02:51	Noise										Start Profile 3 from 2000'
15:03:33	Noise										FL030
15:04:35	50	0.06	380								FL040
15:06:54	120	0.06									FL050
15:07:50	Noise										FL060
15:08:45	Noise										FL070
15:09:43	10	0.06									FL080
15:10:44	10	0.06									FL090
15:11:38	8	0.06									FL100
15:12:34	8	0.06									FL110
15:13:31	3	0.06									FL120

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B135**Date:** 27/09/2005

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to PC B135_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data B135_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to the directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS	21/10/05	
3) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: B135 b) Path name: MFDDATA:B135_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: 0 if unknown e) End time: 240000 if unknown	24/10/05	
4) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: B135 b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: Use the most recent calibration file. Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]	24/10/05	Note the calibration file used FFSSP_CAL23082005.TXT
5) In PVWAVE a) enter: !path=!path+',mrfb:[pms.proc]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! b) write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:B135_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:B135_mfdX','pmsdata:B135_m5procffssp',/auto 1st argument is output file from 5) 2nd argument is the MFD 3rd argument is the new FFSSP data file in M5 format c) exit	24/10/05	
6) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B135_m5procffssp b) Datset: mfddata:B135_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter updated MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	24/10/05	All completed as shown

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B135**Date:** 27/09/2005

B) 2D PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer B135.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
2) Zip up file on PC (B135.zip)		
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS		
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B135.zip	24/10/05	
6) In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B135.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B135_seadas.dat iii) exit	24/10/05	Complete, no read errors
7) run MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B135 c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B135_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	121500 163000 24/10/05	
8) 2D image display and printing Quick look at image blocks if required In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' i) WAVE> IMAGEDISPLAY a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B135 c) IWC plot: N d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Time interval (sec): 0 for every image block nominal 5 sec Preparation of imagery for Core data product iii) WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA:		This section is optional

b) Flight number: B135 c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time 0 if unknown e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks 10 iv) exit PVWAVE Creates files	121500 163000 10 PMSDATA:	FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_B135_2Dx_IMAGES.PS
ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC		
Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter		
Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files	24/10/05	2D-C looks OK throughout 2D-P noisy after climb to high level – OK for most Cu sampling runs prior to 150000
9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO		
a) Flight number: B135 b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: Hit enter d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data	0	As noted in operator log
e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:B135_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty h) Start time: 0 if unkdown i) End time: 240000 if unknown j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown l) Coefficient choice: 2 m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:B135_PROC2D	0 121500 163000 0.2 8 2 25/10/05	Note the particle type
10) In PVWAVE		
i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:B135_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:B135_M5PROC2D' iii) exit	25/10/05	
11) MODIFY		
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B135_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:B135_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	25/10/05	completed

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 135

Date: 27th September 2005

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
XR5M GPS		Y	FFSSP		Y
Cruciform GPS		N	PCASP		Y
Satcom C		Y	2D-P		Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-C		Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope		N
De-Iced Temp		Y	SID 1		N
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 2		Y
Heimann		N	HVPS		N
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP25		N
G. Eastern		Y	CIP100		N
J. Williams		Y			
Nevzorov		Y			
TWC		N			
FWVS		N	Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC		N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC		Y
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI		Y
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	Y	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP		N
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer		N
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters		N
“ JO1D	Y	y	AMS		Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS		N			
MARSS		N			
DEIMOS		N	<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES		N	NIR TDLAS		N
SWS		N	2BT O3		N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC		N
Ozone		Y	PEROXIDE		N
SO2		Y	Formaldehyde		N
NOX		Y	ADA		N
CO		Y	CPI		N
ORAC		N	NOxy		N
PAN		N	PTRMS		N
PERCA		n	Bag Sampling		N
WAS		n	Tube Sampling		N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B135

Date: 27th September 2005

Instruments

1. TWC not fitted
2. Aft console Horace display 10 minutes behind real time
3. Smudge on Foreward facing camera
4. Upper pyrgometer noisy initaly and for last hour of flight
5. Lower pyrgometer zero follows the signal exactly
6. CCN – worked OK but a few internal problems which requires some work on the ground
7. Flight manager laptop – ethernet link problematic
8. 2DP – fine for the flight but falls over at high altitude
9. SATCOM-C handset ringing but no one there when answered. Bob got a message fault when he tried to ring from ground. Rang the fourth time but could not hear.

Aircraft

1. Airstairs u/s (hydraulic leak).
- 2.

Satcom H Calls

Incoming 2 but no one there when answered

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following logs are not available for flight B135:

Log	Reason
De-brief	Sortie De-brief yet to be created by Jonathan Smith
CVI	No log is ever taken for CVI
Core Chemistry	Unattended Operation - no log taken
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM
SID	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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Flight B135 15:07:40

Heading 74 deg Speed 219 knots Height 5.8kft Press 816mb

Lat 55.6N Long 6.6W Wind 18 ms-1/ 261 deg

Temp -2.06C Dewpoint -4.25C

From 14:29:00 to now

Current values		
STATIC PRESSURE	816.46	mb
++++ DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-2.07	deg C
++++ DEW POINT	-4.25	deg C